

The French speaking Patent Information User Group is 30 years old!

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First Act

It is the story of a professional association. It is the story of profession which is closely linked to the environment in which it evolved. It is the story of the French speaking Patent Information User Group, the CFIB^{[1],[2]}

This year the CFIB is 30 years old in 2018.

Come back for a few minutes to 1988, when nobody had ever heard about this association.

Indeed, at our time and age, our youth would certainly be lost if suddenly they were sent back to the 1980's. They would discover the first computers, with no comparison with actual ones, running in DOS (no Microsoft Windows), no internet ... and yes, no smartphones either.

In these years, only a very few patent databases slowly became available to companies. One needs to understand that it was the start of a new age with computers starting to become relatively cheaper, and that data were previously saved at best on magnetic tapes or on microfilms.

Working myself in the Chemical sector, I am tempted to write that only two players were active in the patent databases field: Chemical Abstracts^[3] and Derwent^[4], the first one specific to the chemical world, the second one to patents, whatever the field.

As such, it is only logical that this new group, which was birthed in the offices of Elf-Aquitaine on December 14th 1988, would be named "Club Derwent".

What characterizes this association? All of its members are French, coming from large companies. This is a club where you can become a member only by invitation. It exists by facts, without any legal or official status.

CFIB was not the first such specific group in Europe. At this time two other similar professional ones existed in Europe: the Patent Documentation Group (PDG)⁵, born nearly 30 years before, and the "Werkgemeenschap Octrooi-informatie Nederland" (WON)^[6], the Dutch equivalent to CFIB.

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The first one is an international organization, membership is not free, restricted to large companies, and travels in Europe are required.

The later, as written above, is focused on Dutch Speaking professionals.

Everything was in place for the creation of a new association in France!

From a competitive point of view, it is quite important that the French companies have something to say with respect to future developments of the Derwent database and for knowledge exchanges between members, with the opportunities to send back requests for improvements as needed. This will be some kind of “lobbying” group.

The club will organize one or two half days meeting each year. Most of them are occurring in Paris, the rest will take place outside of the capital for the whole day. Each meeting is hosted by a member and summary bullets are written by “rotating secretaries”.

Act 2

With time, Information Technology (IT) evolves, and the association evolves too!

The Derwent database is not alone on the market anymore. New databases begin to emerge, for example QPat from Questel^[7]: It is therefore time to broaden the scope of our activities.

As such, a new focus is defined in 1996: « Everything which is in relation to patent information ».

A direct follow up is a name modification, we are now speaking about the “Club d’Information Brevet”, “Patent Information Club”, CIB.

But nothing lasts forever, and sometimes you just miss one person and nothing is working correctly anymore. As such, at the end of the ’90’s, with the departure from Mr Yves Dubosc, the movement will enter a hibernation phase. It will be a short one as Ms Colette Hedon will take back the reigns in the early 2000’s and a second name change will occur to become the “French Club of Patent Information Users”, CFIB.

A name which will not last long, as a last modification occurs in 2005 towards the “French Speaking Club for Patent Information Users”, still CFIB ⁸. Hence, CFIB begins accepting members from Luxemburg, Switzerland, Belgium and other French speaking countries.

The number of members significantly increases to 91 in 2005. From then on, any patent information professional may ask to join the user group, with the exception of patent information providers.

Each meeting becomes an opportunity to develop a professional network, with one of the objectives being expertise exchanges between professionals. And all of this is done within a friendly atmosphere towards a non-profit organization.

Act 3

2009: Anne-Gaëlle Darmont and Colette Hedon, with a small motivated band of others decide it is time to move on and transform the CFIB towards an association with a legal recognition.

Everything is reviewed, from A to Z...statutes are written and deposited in a legal jurisdiction.

These new statutes include a drastic modification as now an Executive Board is required: Anne-Gaëlle Darmont will be the President, Colette Hedon being Vice-President.

Six other members are part of this initial executive team: Fabienne Piron, Cécile Boyer-Joubert, Muriel Bourgeois-Tassanary, Didier Bernard, Philippe Bodart and Frédéric Baudour.

Another major modification is the adoption of a CFIB budget, by a very modest yearly contribution being required from the members. Very modest indeed, because the objective is clearly to be a non-profit community for the members and by the members, and not a lobby of multinational industrial companies.

All these structural modifications are once again the result of the World evolution and of our profession evolution. It is indeed at this time, precisely in 2008, that the « Confederacy of European Patent Information User Group » (CEPIUG) ^[9] is created, with CFIB being a founding member and with Anne-Gaëlle Darmont a member of its board.

And why the creation of CEPIUG at this time? Because the project for a Patent Information Professional Certification ¹⁰ starts to emerge.

This new environment will be beneficial for inter-association exchanges: CFIB presentations at WON, Certification project presentation at CFIB, external recognition (presentations & posters at IPI Confex ^[11], but also opportunities to chair some of its sessions ...)

Act 4

CFIB becomes proactive in this new configuration: working groups are created, initially focused on tools used for patent information searching, Cartography and also training.

The latter will become one of the association's main development vectors, in the frame of Training & Education: a partnership is signed in 2014 with the "Institut Français de la Propriété Industrielle"

(INPI) ^[12] and another one with the European Institute for Enterprise and Intellectual Property (IEEPI) in 2016 ¹³.

CFIB members are recognized for their expertise, so now they can share it via training sessions organized by both institutes.

Another new important vector is the creation in the early 2010 of an internal newsletter: « Le Courrier du CFIB ». Published approximately every two months, this newsletter is exclusively available to the members and contains articles relative to the life of the association, feedback from conference attendances, feedback from new tool trials, news from the working groups, external events and stories, etc. To celebrate the 30 years of CFIB, le “Courrier” evolves into the “e-Mag”. This new format looks like a professional journal, ads excluded.

Lastly let’s emphasize again that the networking is a third main vector of our association, not only during annual meetings but also through job offers published on our website, questions asked via our forum, etc.

New members are entering the board, others are leaving. 2014 sees Anne-Gaëlle Darmont leaving, called by new challenges. Since then the president chair is assumed by Frederic Baudour.

The CFIB is now, more than ever, a key player in the patent information field, with representation at the « Standing Advisory Committee before the European Patent Office » (SACEPO) ^[14], but also at the « International Standards Board for Qualified Patent Information Professionals » (ISBQPIP) ^[15]; we also continue our involvement at CEPIUG, Muriel Bourgeois-Tassanary being its new president.

The main objective of the association is now the promotion of the patent information profession, the promotion of its members, and the CFIB is not afraid to let it be known. As an example, let’s cite the common letter sent by CFIB and BEPIUG (Belgian Patent Information User Group) ¹⁶ in order to request significant modification for the Certification project, when no one had reacted until then. Latest version of the articles & regulations are now in-line with our professional profile.

Conclusion

Can we even speak about a conclusion? This is not the end by far. On this year 2018, CFIB counts more than 160 members, which places it as the second European association relative to our profession in terms of numbers of members ^[17], a little bit behind the WON (which has somewhat different status)

Fig. 1: Number of members per user groups associated to CEPIUG, October 2017 (data provided with courtesy by CEPIUG)

Fig. 2: CFIB members’ breakdown by gender (CFIB – 2018)

The balance from male/female members is quite fair considering our various professional environments and technical domains. It has been stable for the last decade and gets a positive influence on overall network and communication.

Fig. 3: CFIB members’ breakdown by type of activity sector (CFIB – 2018)

While more than two third of the total number of members comes from Industry, we again notice that vendors are excluded from the Club. Outsourcing agents also counts free-lancers in Patent Information activity but are not dominant. Under “others” category, we mainly retrieve students and retirees still very active within our community!

Fig. 4: CFIB members’ breakdown by French speaking country of origin (CFIB – 2018)

From Figure 4, we can acknowledge the fact that France is covering two third of the total members, which is driven by the history of the user group. Nevertheless, Belgium and Switzerland, both being a multi-lingual country, have set a growing membership since the last decade.

Ideas are not missing, as more and more projects see the light, often more than available resources. Future is shaped and driven by few but motivated members and more to come in the next few years.

It is a game worth playing: indeed recognition is happening, with invitation to participate in organizing major events, for example, the first CEPIUG conference in Milano (September 2018) and also the EPOPIC (European Patent Office Information Patent Conference) ^[18] in November 2018 in Brussels.

This is the story of our association. An association which has evolved with its environment and over time. An association which will continue to evolve for and by its members.

Thanks

I would like to thank Miss. Colette Hedon and Anne-Gaëlle Darmont, and also Mr Yves Dubosc and Luc Petitpas for their kind support when writing this article. Many thanks my former colleague and friend David Breiner of Boehringer Ingelheim in the U.S. for additional translation support of this article.

Muriel Bourgeois-Tassanary played the ghost role of reviewing and amending the document, formatting endnotes and providing illustrations. As per our long time & friendly relationship, she is a well-deserved contributor to this non-ending journey.

And of course we need to thanks all the CFIB members who are each contributing to keep this nice story alive.

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Hyperlinks have been validated on July 10th 2018